

Deliverable D12.3

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1 Executive summary

WP12 outlines a user-training plan for the final year of the BioMedBridges project. This will involve the development of online training modules in collaboration with the technical work packages and developers from across the ESFRI BMS research infrastructures. Plans are presented to ensure that these modules have sustainable impact for end users of BioMedBridges services.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Deliver short courses to train project participants in relevant areas of bioinformatics that are outside of their current experience and necessary to build crosslinks between the data resources of the BMS RIs	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Produce documentation on the resources developed, for use initially within the project but ultimately by the end-users of the integrated services developed by BioMedBridges	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Deliver short courses enabling end-users of the biomedical research infrastructures to benefit from the developments of work packages 3–11	<input type="checkbox"/>	

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

WP12 Training – has coordinated or contributed to the development, organisation and delivery of 6 knowledge exchange workshops within the

BioMedBridges project (see Supplement 1: BioMedBridges Knowledge Exchange Workshops). These have allowed project partners to come to a shared understanding of the challenges – both technical and social – in developing interoperable biomedical informatics services bridging several research infrastructures. WP12 has also delivered a full end-user training course in collaboration with EU-OPENSREEN on the topic of high-throughput chemical screening.

Following guidance from the Executive Steering Committee at the end of 2013, WP12 developed a user-training plan – updated and presented as this deliverable – for the final year of the project. This plan involves the creation of online training modules to support key project services. These online modules will have a greater legacy and a wider reach to BioMedBridges end-users than the originally proposed conference-based workshops and face-to-face training courses outlined in the original description of work.

3.2 Who are BioMedBridges's users?

Our concept of an 'end user' has shifted throughout the project. BioMedBridges is developing tools, databases and guidelines that will improve the underlying interoperability between bioinformatics and biomedical informatics resources, with a focus on those produced by or used by the BMS-RIs. The immediate beneficiaries of the project's deliverables are bioinformaticians and developers; BioMedBridges's outputs will enable bioinformaticians and developers to build the next generation of biomedical informatics resources aimed at bench-based molecular life scientists, clinical researchers and clinical practitioners – the communities that we typically refer to as 'end users' of the research infrastructures.

We feel that we will best serve the goals of the project, and the needs of the research infrastructures going forward, if we focus on:

1. Supporting bioinformaticians to make use of the data provided by the BMS-RIs; and

2. Supporting developers to create new resources, or enhance existing resources, aimed at end users of the BMS-RIs.

In many cases it would be inappropriate to develop training materials for bench-based molecular life scientists, clinical researchers and clinical practitioners on BioMedBridges's resources because these audiences would not be best placed to make direct use of BioMedBridges's deliverables.

3.3 Gathering input for the user training plan

3.3.1 Training needs survey

During March 2014 WP12 sent out a survey to the coordinators, project and operational managers, and training representatives from all 13 ESFRI-BMS research infrastructures to gain a greater understanding of their training needs. A total of 45 respondents completed the survey.

The survey asked respondents to rank ten competencies in 'big data' for importance to their RI. These competencies were ranked as (highest first):

1. Relevance of software, data and tools for your research infrastructure
2. Interoperability of data across research infrastructures
3. Accessing data relevant to your research infrastructure
4. Submitting data relevant to your research infrastructure
5. Appraising the benefits/drawbacks of data-sharing and open-access for your research infrastructure
6. Annotating/curating data for your research infrastructure
7. Knowledge of what e-infrastructure can do for your research infrastructure
8. Supporting data users of your research infrastructure
9. Designing and maintaining databases for your research infrastructure
10. Writing and implementing a data management plan for your research infrastructure

See Appendix 1 for a full breakdown of the responses provided.

3.4 Interviews with WP leaders

WP12 held 1:1 discussions with BioMedBridges WP leaders, or a nominee, to gain a better understanding of training needs within the project and in relation to the ESFRI BMS. These discussions were held via a combination of face-to-face meetings, Skype calls and email exchanges. Those contacted were:

- WP3 – Nathalie Conte, Morris Swertz
- WP4 – Julie McMurry
- WP6 – Gabriella Rustici
- WP9 – Martyn Winn, Ardan Patwardhan
- WP10 – Ugis Sarkans

These discussions led to the identification of BioMedBridges services that met prioritization criteria for the development of training materials. The meetings allowed for the chance to sketch out concepts for modules, agree timelines for development and identify key project members that could work with WP12 on these tasks. They also provided an opportunity to understand future requirements for the training materials, with which ESFRI BMS the services would reside following BioMedBridges and to consider long-term sustainability of the training resources.

Initial discussions were unable to be held with work packages 5, 7 and 8. However, since the initial round of interviews were conducted, discussions have been held with relevant groups representing these areas of the project.

Following a workshop hosted by WP5 (see Supplement 1 for “Knowledge Exchange Workshop: Personal data in the life sciences”) it was agreed that a module would be developed around this topic.

It is hoped that a module can be developed in collaboration with WP7, but it is noted that the PhenoBridge prototype discovery tool will not be delivered until month 48. Instead the module will focus on the ZOOMA tool used for the co-annotation of mouse datasets in Deliverable 7.2.

Format of user training

Face-to-face workshops and courses are widely acknowledged as being an effective way of delivering training for continuing professional development. However, they are expensive to develop, organise and deliver; they also require trainees to be away from their daily role at a specific time and often for several days, which may not coincide with the individual's need for training in a particular topic. Face-to-face courses typically only reach a small proportion of those who require training, owing to limited scalability.

Therefore WP12 will develop short, self-contained modules in an online format. These online modules will be accessible to all users of BioMedBridges services – and beyond – and have the added advantage of being easy to maintain. In this way they will become part of the sustainable legacy of the project and will be retained by the infrastructure responsible for maintaining the service.

These online modules will focus on building conceptual understanding of the science behind the services, rather than step-by-step instruction on how to use the service. They will introduce the service and explain the science behind the tool, why it is required, who it is designed for and how it can be used to build 'data bridges' between disparate services.

3.4.1 Online training

EMBL-EBI has developed a user-friendly e-learning platform with which to build and publish online courses to support its bioinformatics databases, tools and services (www.ebi.ac.uk/training/online/). In October 2014 >17,000 users (based on unique IP addresses) accessed the resource. Publishing BioMedBridges' modules in Train online will therefore help to raise awareness of the services developed by the project, supporting the work of WP2. These modules will be branded appropriately to indicate BioMedBridges and other research infrastructure involvement. Added functionality will also enable users to quickly find all BioMedBridges courses.

All materials in Train online are produced under a [Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International Public License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/), allowing the materials to be re-used by anyone provided that the original authors are acknowledged.

EMBL-EBI also assigns materials in Train online with a DOI, allowing them to be cited in the same manner as journal publications and providing recognition for the authors. This will further enhance sustainability and dissemination of BioMedBridges outcomes. This will contribute towards the list of publications resulting from BioMedBridges.

3.5 Prioritizing training module ideas

As documented in the BioMedBridges services registry, the project is developing a diverse collection of services and tools to support the integration and interoperability of biological data across Europe (Figure 1). These services vary in scope and scale, from small but vital technical components to large tools that fill current gaps in data infrastructure.

Name	Type	Description	Topics	Maturity	Functions	Docs	Funding
AMPs-NMR	Tool	NMR protein structure refinement	Structure determination...	not specifi...			BMB
BBMRI-EU catalog	Database	Database of collections of biomaterial and ass...	Biobank Data search an...	not specifi...			BMB
BBMRI-NL catalog	Database	Database of collections of biomaterial and ass...	Biobank Data search an...	not specifi...			BMB
BBMRI-Portal	Database	A reference for scientists seeking information ...	Laboratory resources	not specifi...			BMB
Clinical Trials Info	Tool		Data search and retrieval	not specifi...			BMB
ESFRI BMS Online	Database			not specifi...			BMB
FindGeo	Tool	Determine metal coordination geometry	Bioinorganic chemistry	not specifi...			BMB
GenoBridge	Tool	TBD Natalie is working on this as of late Sept...	Genotype phenotype	not specifi...			BMB
Legal Tool TBN	Tool			not specifi...			BMB
Mapping and regio	Database			not specifi...			BMB
MaxOcc	Tool	Numerical assessments about the maximum ...	Protein dynamics	not specifi...			BMB
MetalPDB	Database	Knowledge on metal sites in biological macro...	Bioinorganic chemistry ...	not specifi...			BMB
Metals2	Tool	Allows two metal-binding sites to be structura...	Bioinorganic chemistry ...	not specifi...			BMB
MOLGENIS.compass	Tool	Workflow tool useful for core facilities to creat...	Data handling	not specifi...	Sequence alignment Dat...		BMB
MOLGENIS	Framework	For biologists MOLGENIS is a suite of web dat...	Data management Data...	not specifi...			BMB
MousePhenotype	Database	International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium ...	Systemic phenotyping ...	not specifi...			BMB
myEquivalents	Tool	myEquivalents is a cross reference service, th...	Cross References Linke...	BETA	Cross references		BMB
Ontology Tree Vie	Tool			not specifi...			BMB
PIMS LIMS	Tool	A Laboratory Information Management Syste...	Protein production LIMS...		Data retrieval (database...		BBSRC CCP4 BMB
PIMS	Tool	Laboratory Information Management System ...		not specifi...			BMB
Shape Matching T	Tool	Searching and annotation of volume data fro...	Structural biology				BMB
Tools Registry	Database			not specifi...			BMB ELIXIR-DK
UniChem	Database	Rapid cross-referencing of chemical structure...	Data search and retriev...				BMB
WebMicroscope	Package	Platform for virtual microscopy		not specifi...			BMB
xnat.bigr.nl	Tool	TBD. Will serve the data that is currently only...		not specifi...			BMB
xnat.bmia.nl	Tool	TBD. set up in collaboration with CTMM TraIT...		not specifi...			BMB

Figure 1: BioMedBridges services registry showing BioMedBridges developed tools and services

The development of training materials for these services ideally requires several factors to be in place:

- Maturity of service – at least in beta release and unlikely to change much in utility or function
- Stable technology – rapid technology advances lead to training materials becoming out-dated rapidly
- Available expertise – the development of advanced technical training needs input both from the technical developers most intimately associated with each BioMedBridges service, and training professionals capable of transforming this technical input into user-friendly courses.

Given that the delivery of many BioMedBridges services falls late in the project timeline, there is not sufficient time to develop training for all the services. Therefore we have used the following methodology to prioritise the top ideas for further development.

3.5.1 Module ranking methodology

We have developed a multivariate methodology to score both the usefulness and the feasibility of each course concept generated by our training needs analysis. This methodology scores courses according to four criteria:

- Does it fulfil competency requirements?
- How many RIs are bridged?
- Will services be developed in time to generate course materials?
- Do we have commitment from technical personnel to develop course materials?

Does it fulfil competency requirements?

The interviews with WP leaders and technical leads generated module outlines for several services. Each of these were scored against the list of desired competencies from the training needs survey. A ‘competency factor’ was calculated as follows

Competency factor =

(# of competencies met)

x

(proportion of respondents requesting each competency)

How many RIs are bridged?

BioMedBridges services aim to facilitate the integration of biomedical data across multiple research infrastructures. To include this in to the methodology a 'bridging factor' was incorporated into our analysis. This simply calculates the proportion of the 13 research infrastructures linked or 'bridged' by the service in question.

Will services be ready in time to create module materials?

Many BioMedBridges services are still in development, with completion dates scheduled close to the end of the project (Q2-4 Year 4). This is a significant risk factor as there will be little time left to create module materials. Each module idea has been assigned a score for feasibility as follows:

- 3 = service is live
- 2 = service due to be live by Dec 2014
- 1 = service due to be live by June 2015
- 0 = service due to be live Dec 2014

Is there commitment from technical personnel to develop module materials?

Commitment to draft module materials is a critical factor in the development of any technical training. WP12's personnel can support development by refining module outlines, providing the framework for course authoring, editing module drafts, helping to create questions and exercises, testing the module in its final stages, and in the publishing and promotion of the finished module. However, the developers are the people who best understand the services, the science behind them and how end users are intended to make use of them. Technical commitment was scored as followed:

- 2 = author agreed
- 1 = author suggested by WP leader but not confirmed
- 0 = no commitment from author

3.5.2 Overall score

These four factors are multiplied to generate an overall score encompassing both the feasibility and the usefulness to the RIs of each course concept. Supplement 3 (see attached xlsx file) illustrates this methodology by providing scores for six module concepts generated during our recent interviews with BioMedBridges WP personnel.

3.5.3 User training plan

The above methodology was followed to create a spreadsheet of potential modules for online training, covering a number of the BioMedBridges services and tools. As the project continues in its final year the spreadsheet will be updated to ensure that delivery of modules is met and kept in line with the final delivery of services by other WPs (**See Supplement 3: User training plan**).

3.6 Training modules

The planned training modules are outlined below:

- An introduction to ontologies – outlining the concepts of bio-ontologies and the various applications to which they have been applied within BioMedBridges. Content will be derived in part from the “Practical solutions with ontologies” knowledge exchange workshop
- Ethical, legal and social issues – a conceptual module that highlights the handling of sensitive data and samples. Content will be derived in part from the “Personal data in the life sciences” knowledge exchange workshop, as well input from the BioMedBridges ethics review
- User experience design – building on the WP2 deliverable 12.3 “Definition of a user-centred design process with the technical work packages” this module will provide an overview of ensuring biological data services are developed with the end user in mind
- Data standards – a conceptual module that introduces data standards and their role in facilitating integration and interoperability of biological data, and provides an overview of key standards used within

BioMedBridges. Content will be derived in part from the WP3 standards and data integration workshops

- Shape-matching software – a conceptual module that will introduce the scientific and technical understanding behind the WP9 shape-matching software and how it allows the integration of different types of biological data
- Services registry quick tour – this module will provide an introduction to the basic functionality of the services registry
- Standards registry quick tour – this module will provide an introduction to the basic functionality of the standards registry
- Image data analysis quick tour – this module will provide an introduction to the basic functionality of the Cellular Microscopy Phenotype Ontology
- Linking data-sets via ontologies – a module that will build on the “An introduction to ontologies” module and demonstrate the use of the ZOOMA tool and how it was used to link data using ontologies
- Legal assessment tool quick tour – this module will provide an introduction to the basic functionality of the legal assessment tool

Additional modules could be created if time allows. These would take the format of short introductory ‘quick tours’ of a specific BioMedBridges service. They would provide a brief introduction in basic functionality, directing new users in how to begin utilising the resource. This approach would lack a more detailed explanation of the science and technology behind the resource.

3.7 Sustainability

As outlined above, EMBL-EBI will continue to host the online training modules following the end of BioMedBridges. The ESFRI BMS infrastructures that continue to support and develop the underlying services will be involved to ensure the continued sustainability and applicability of the training resources in the future.

3.8 Progress update

Since July 2014 WP12 has begun work on delivery of training modules that will support BioMedBridges services. This work has involved liaising with various WP leaders and their technical staff to understand services and how materials can be presented to introduce the resource and the underlying science. Figure 2 below illustrates progress on the prioritized modules and those that can be developed with support from technical staff across the project.

Module	2014						2015											
	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
An introduction to ontologies																		
Ethical, Legal and Social Issues																		
User experience design																		
Data standards																		
Shape-matching software quick tour					*													
Services registry quick tour	*																	
Standards registry quick tour						*												
Image data analysis quick tour	*																	
Linking data-sets via ontologies	*																	
Legal assessment tool quick tour																		

Figure 2 Orange shows develop phase, green indicates expected time module will be live. Asterisk (*) indicates when relevant service will be live

4 Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

5 Adjustments made

This deliverable no longer covers the previously stated delivery of workshops at conferences. This approach to training has been replaced by the creation of online training modules instead. These will be able to reach a greater number of individual scientists across Europe, and beyond, than face-to-face training could.

6 Background information

This deliverable relates to WP 12; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DoW) is included below.

WP 12 Title: Training
 Lead: Cath Brooksbank (EMBL)
 Participants: EMBL

This work package will provide training on the tools and services developed within the BioMedBridges project.

Work package number	WP12	Start date or starting event:	month 1
Work package title	Training		
Activity Type	COORD		
Participant number	1:EMBL		
Person-months per participant	42		

Objectives

1. Deliver short courses to train project participants in relevant areas of bioinformatics that are outside of their current experience and necessary to build crosslinks between the data resources of the BMS RIs.
2. Produce documentation on the resources developed, for use initially within the project but ultimately by the end-users of the integrated services developed by BioMedBridges.
3. Deliver short courses enabling end-users of the biomedical research infrastructures to benefit from the developments of work packages 3–11.

Task 1: Workshops for project participants and documentation of resources developed

This task will deliver four workshops aimed at the BioMedBridges project participants during the first three years of the project, beginning towards the end of year 1. The topics of these workshops will be defined by the personnel working on each of the technical work packages, and coordinated by a full-time scientific training and outreach officer whose duties will be divided between this work package and WP2 (outreach). This individual will maintain

an overview of the entire programme, work with the representatives from the technical work packages to develop the programmes for each workshop, ensure that the workshops are promoted effectively to relevant people within the project, and chair each workshop. The personnel working on the technical work packages will therefore need to dedicate a small but significant part of their time (estimated at two person months per work package throughout the project) to developing their workshop programmes and delivering training.

Workshop topics

Suggested topics include (but are not limited to) the following. This is likely to evolve, and workshop topics may merge or become further specialised as the project progresses.

- Practical solutions to interoperability standards development. This workshop will be led by WP3 (standards) and the main target audience will be WP4 (technical integration). The goal will be to enable those integrating the different BMS RI data sets to do so using an agreed set of standards and molecular identifiers defined by WP3. Input from the use cases will ensure that discussions and actions remain rooted in practical solutions to real data integration problems. The technology watch group will select trainers who can educate the delegates about any new developments beyond BioMedBridges that might provide solutions to ongoing interoperability problems within the project.
- Practical solutions to secure data access. This workshop will be led by WP5 (Secure access) and the main target audience will be WP4 (technical integration). The goal of the workshop will be to enable those constructing the links between the BMS RIs' data sets to do so in a way that respects the rights of patients and healthy volunteers without impeding legitimate research. This workshop will include sessions led by experts on ethical and legal aspects of personal data sharing, and may involve representatives from patient groups.
- Practical solutions to development of web services. This will be led by WP4 (technical integration) and the main target audience will be the use cases (WPs 6–10). The goal will be to inform the development of programmatic access to integrated data sets spanning several BMS RIs and to develop workflows that reflect the needs of researchers using the BMS RIs. Input from the use cases will ensure that discussions and actions remain rooted in practical solutions to real data integration problems. The technology watch group will select trainers who can educate the delegates about any new web service or search technologies beyond BioMedBridges.
- Practical solutions to database development and interoperability. This will be led by WP4 (technical integration) and the target audience will be the use cases. The goal of the workshop will be to stimulate the development of integrated search tools spanning multiple BMS-RIs. This workshop will also include opportunities for the different use cases to learn from each other.

Workshops will be short and intensive (2–3 days), based on a combination of presentations, discussions, practical computer-based problem solving, and documentation writing. Each workshop will be hosted by a different BMS RI.

As these workshops are intended to define, and begin to action, a set of practical solutions, numbers of delegates will be kept small and that the ratio of trainers to delegates high – typically 5 trainers and 20 delegates in each workshop making 25 in total. Logistics and administrative support (registrations, inviting trainers, travel arrangements, answering delegates' queries, etc.) will be provided by the BioMedBridges Project manager with support from the EMBL-EBI's Outreach and Training Team. We will use events management systems and standard operating procedures that are already successfully running at the EMBL-EBI. The fact that we have considerable experience of running courses and workshops, and tried and tested systems for doing so, represents excellent added value for BioMedBridges.

Documentation

An outcome of each workshop will be the production of documentation to support the target audience of each workshop in implementing what they have learned. The trainers and trainees will take joint responsibility for writing clear guidelines for a specific topic. On the last day of each workshop, the delegates will define a set of frequently asked questions, and will work with the speakers/trainers to produce a clear set of answers. The BioMedBridges Scientific Training Officer will compile, edit and make this documentation available, initially to project members, and ultimately to end-users of the services developed by BioMedBridges. Members of personnel from the technical work packages will take responsibility for keeping this documentation up to date.

Task 2: Training for end-users of the BMS RIs.

In the fourth year of the project we will deliver training to end users of the integrated services developed by BioMedBridges. We will deliver two courses, which will be a combination of lectures, demos, discussions and hands-on computer-based tutorials. Personnel from the use cases will deliver these courses, and each course will be aimed at a different target audience – one focused on fundamental research, the other on translational and clinical research. By the end of year 3 of BioMedBridges, we anticipate that the individual BMS research infrastructures will be funded and are likely to be running training programmes for their own stakeholders. Using materials developed for the abovementioned courses, and our extensive network of training contacts developed through other initiatives such as the IMI Education and Training projects, we will also make the most of any opportunities to support these training programmes. We will also identify appropriate conferences at which we can offer training workshops.

Appendix 1: BioMedBridges Knowledge Exchange Workshops

Details for knowledge exchange workshops and courses run as part of the project can be found at www.biomedbridges.eu/training.

Appendix 2: BioMedBridges training needs survey, March 2014

This survey was developed to help identify training priorities across the ESFRI BMS with respect to BioMedBridges and to guide WP12 training plans until the end of the project in December 2015. It was disseminated via the BioMedBridges Technical Coordination Committee mailing list across project members, their respective RIs and partner institutes. Responses were collected prior to the 2014 AGM in Florence, and again in the subsequent 14 days following the meeting's conclusion. 45 respondents began the survey, and 41 (91.1%) completed it. Figures 3 & 4 detail the background of respondents. Figures 5, 6 & 7 detail the responses given in the priority ranking exercise for project managers/coordinators, technical staff and RI users respectively. Figure 8 provides a combined view of all stakeholder priorities.

Figure 3 Training survey respondents by RI (n-45)

This question asked respondents their RI affiliation.

Figure 4 Training survey respondents by job role

This question asked respondents their job role.

Figure 5 High-priority skills for project managers/coordinators

Figure 6 High-priority skills for technical staff

Figure 7 High-priority skills for RI users

Figure 8 High priority skills across all stakeholders

Appendix 3: User training plan

Supplement 2: User training plan

	Course concept											
Competency from training needs survey	% requiring this competency	An introduction to ontologies	Ethical, legal and social issues	User experience design	Data standards	Shape-matching software	Services registry quick tour	Standards registry quick tour	Image data analysis quick tour	Linking data-sets via ontologies	Legal assessment tool quick tour	
Data management	0.60	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1
Database design	0.60	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Supporting data users	0.60	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
e-infrastructure	0.60	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Annotating/curating	0.65	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Data sharing	0.65	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
Submitting data	0.70	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Accessing data	0.75	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Data interoperability	0.80	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
Relevant software	0.80	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1

No. Ris bridged		13	13	2	3	2	13	13	3	2	2
Which Ris bridged?		ALL	ALL	ELIXIR, EATRIS	ALL	ELIXIR, INSTRUMENT	ALL	ALL	ELIXIR, Eubi, EATRIS	ELIXIR, InfraFrontier	ELIXIR, BBMRI
WP responsible		3, 12	5	4	3	9	3	3	6	3, 7	5, 10
Author		Tom, James Malone, Simon Jupp	Murat Sariyar, Sarah Morgan, Carol Smees, Irene Schluender	Francis Rowland	Chao Pang, Morris Swertz, Nathalie Conte	Ardan Patwardhan	ELIXIR-DK	Chao Pang	Gabriella Rustici	Tony Burdett, Nathalie Conte	Murat Sariyar

Expected completion date		Jan-15	Dec-15	Mar-15	Mar-15	Jun-15	Mar-15	Jun-15	Sep-15	Sep-15	?
BMB tools featured		N/A	CONCEPT	WP7 use case	Standards registry	Shape-matching server	Services registry	Standards registry	CMPO, Xnat	zoomai	Legal tool
Sustainability plan		workshop	Legal tool	ELIXIR hub?	BBMRI-NL?	CCP4 courses; EMDB	ELIXIR-DK?	BBMRI-NL?	Eubi?	ELIXIR hub?	EBI

Competency factor (No. competencies addressed x proportion of respondents requesting this skill)			4.75	4.80	1.35	4.15	2.80	2.80	3.35	4.05	4.10	4.00
Bridges factor (% Ris bridged)		1.00	1.00	0.15	0.23	0.15	1.00	1.00	0.23	0.15	0.15	0.15
Feasibility score (scores 3 if service already live 2 if service due to be live by Dec 2014, 1 if service due to be live by June 2015 and 0 if service due to be live Dec 2015)			3	2	3	1	2	3	2	3	3	0
Author score (scores 2 if author agreed; 1 if author suggested; 0 if no commitment from author yet)		1	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	1	1
Overall score		14.25	19.20	1.25	1.92	1.72	0.00	13.40	5.61	1.89	0.00	